

Idea of Family in the Select American Children's Literature

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19310731

Abstract:

The present paper is a modest attempt to analyse and explore an idea of family in the select modern American children's literature. The role of family is very crucial in the overall development of a child. The child grows under the proper supervision of family members who bestow love, affection and care, and imbibe cultural, social, and moral values among the children. The family support and encouragement are very significant for the child's recognition and status in the society. In fact, family constructs and shapes the future of the child. However, the role of family goes through a drastic change in the modern era as it appears disrupted and broken due to various causes. The present paper conducts survey of the select American children's books that represents this transition from idealistic family to fragmented family structure in America.

Keywords: *Children's Literature, American Children's Literature, The Nuclear Family, Extended Family, Alternative Family etc.*

Children's literature has always played a pivotal role in shaping how the young readers understand the world around them. More than simple stories for entertainment, children's books function as cultural texts that reflect social values, norms, family structures and expectations. Through narratives and illustrations, children learn about relationships, gender roles, morality, community, and most importantly, the idea of family. As society changes over time, so too does the representation of families in children's literature. The children's literature also projects the transition from a singular, traditional model of the family toward a more diverse, complex, and realistic representation of family life.

Happy families are all alike, Tolstoy told us, but "every unhappy family is unhappy in its own way." The strength children draw from loving parents, siblings, and other relatives and the guiding principles set forth by elders for youngsters to follow remain constant, however

different the tenets or the family structure may have become. The things that cause unhappiness, pain, confusion, and angst, however, vary significantly, reflecting changes in the composition of families and society.

In the early to mid-twentieth century, the American children's literature largely mirrored dominant social ideals rather than challenging them. Families were typically portrayed as stable, harmonious, and morally upright. Parents were assigned clear gender roles i.e. fathers worked outside the home while mothers remained domestic caregivers. The books for young readers emphasized general moral values such as kindness, cooperation, responsibility, and respect for others. Many stories were set in rural or small-town environments, reinforcing a nostalgic image of family life rooted in simplicity and community.

The 1960s marked a gradual shift in the portrayal of families, influenced by major social, political, and cultural changes. While many books

still depicted traditional nuclear families, the tone and content of stories changed. Instead of presenting families as entirely conflict-free, books began to show children experiencing disagreements with parents, feelings of dissatisfaction, or emotional struggles.

Families disintegrating and re-forming are part of life for today's children, and the candour with which authors address painful issues such as death, divorce, intolerance, abuse, and neglect in the early twenty-first century reflects an awareness that children feel the pain of such changes as deeply as adults do. Yet for children, family is still a crucial factor in survival. The bonds of affection and concern; the warmth and shelter of home and its inhabitants, be they many or few; the depth of love and the tenacity that hold families together through hard times; and the thread that ties one generation to the next that keep stories alive from one generation to the next.

Arthur Ransome, an English author and journalist registers his views about the trend in the family stories as follows:

It is now widely acknowledged that concepts of family are socially and culturally constructed, influenced by economic, religious and political trends. Change is also evident in the representations of fictional families from the early nineteenth century to the present day which generally reflect a trend towards more liberal attitudes and subversion of the traditional values.

Stories about the nuclear, extended and alternative families are abundant in the children's fiction. The children and their relationships with their parents and siblings are quite genuine topics of books of children. In certain cases, the childhood of children is spent in close association with family members. Consequently, the family stories for young children frequently present a happy child with loving parents. These stories depict the daily activities such as brushing tooth to preparing food in the kitchen. These are chapter books appealing to newly independent

readers who can relate their daily lives. These stories often display child at play and even explore the relationship between the siblings. Authors such as Lois Lowry and Beverly Cleary with their books 'Anastasia Krupnik' (1979) and 'Ramona Quimby, Age 8' respectively portray the nuclear families. The American writer Lois Lowry 'Anastasia Krupnik' presents ten years old girl Anastasia Krupnik whose world is going to shatter with the arrival of a new baby. It explores her liking and disliking. She keeps a list of the things she loves and she hates in her zealously guarded green notebook. When she learns that her parents are expecting baby, a boy, she considers leaving her family and becoming a Catholic like her best friend, Jennifer. Beverly Cleary's 'Ramona Quimby, Age 8' depicts the white American middle-class family with warmth and interest. It portrays Quimby family and the real concerns of ordinary children.

In the extended family structure, the role of aunts, cousins, and grandparents is quite significant. The books based on the extended family will tell of a child raised by one of the family members in the absence of their parents where a relative functions as a supportive family member. 'The Unmaking of a Rabbit' (1972) by Constance Greene and Patricia MacLachlan's 'Arthur for the Very First Time' are popular examples of this type of family picture. 'The Unmaking of a Rabbit' by Constance Greene focuses on an eleven-year-old boy named Paul, who struggles with loneliness and insecurity while living with his grandmother. Paul is deeply affected by the abandonment of his father and his mother who makes unfulfilled promises. It explores Paul's internal struggles facing as unloved and his parent's strange behaviour. The novel is about his search for an identity and self-worth, the pain of abandonment, moral dilemma and personal growth.

Patricia MacLachlan's 'Arthur for the Very First Time' (1980) is centered on around a

ten-year old boy named Arthur Rasby who suffers on account of family tensions, a new pregnancy in the household, and the absence of friends. He is sent to stay with his eccentric Aunt Elda and Uncle Wrisby on their farm. His experience at the farm with charming people and playful animals triggers his imagination and individuality. It projects a world where children and adults alike learn from their experiences.

The alternative family genre of modern era represents the family structure characterized by not only safe and secure world of healthy and intact families but also of separation, divorce, and single-parent families. It shows the world of stepparents and the stepchildren. It focuses on the conflict faced by the difficulty children and adults encounter in adjusting themselves into these new family surroundings. It occupies significant place in the young reader as it exposes them to true and factual narrative of modern times through alternative family structure. It changes their traditional and stereotype perspective of parents and siblings. The alternative family structure of modern times is main concern of the books such as 'The Night Daddy'(1971) by the Swedish writer Maria Gripe, 'Something to Count On'(1980) by Emily Moore, and 'Mom, the Wolfman and Me'(1972) by Norma Klein. Children's literature in the 1970s increasingly depicted families experiencing real-life difficulties. Stories featured divorced parents, single-parent households, blended families, and extended families where grandparents or other relatives played central care giving roles. They addressed emotional or social challenges faced by children. Themes such as parental separation, grief, loss, illness, and economic hardship became more common.

'The Night Daddy' is centered around a twelve-year old fatherless girl and her

relationship with the night time babysitter. Their bonding is based on mutual respect and companionship. It subverts the typical father figure, instead providing a nurturing and imaginative presence, while the protagonist Julia remains thoughtful and independent. 'Something to Count On' explores ten-year-old Lorraine's behaviour problems at school resulting from her family background and advent of a new teacher in her school solves it with proper understanding.

'Mom, the Wolfman and Me' (1972) by Norma Klein is told from the first-person perspective of an eleven -year-old girl Brett who is living with her mother named Deborah, in New York. It is a story of a fatherless girl and her unmarried mother. It is about unwed mother and illegitimate child who are seeking for the self-affirmation. Brett is concerned about her mother's marriage to normalize her social life.

In conclusion, the portrayal of families in the modern American children's literature reflects broader social transformations. While traditional families remain present, modern children's books increasingly recognize and validate diverse family structures. This shift suggests that children's literature plays an important role in promoting understanding, empathy, and acceptance in young readers.

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